

Technical note on the Automatic Weather Station at Solalex, Cergnement Valley, Alpes Vaudoises, Western Switzerland

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Introduction

A new automatic weather station (AWS) was installed at Solalex, adjacent to the Auberge de Solalex, in the Cergnement valley, Vaudois Alps, Switzerland. The station is designed to provide continuous measurements of local meteorological conditions in a high-alpine environment, complementing existing observations in the surrounding region.

The new station at Solalex replaces a previous installation at the same location and continues observations made between 2010 and 2018 (Guisan et al. 2026). The Solalex station provides an additional observational point in the immediate vicinity of the Vallon de Nant, where three new weather stations have recently been deployed (Miesen et al. 2024). Together, these stations aim to improve the spatial coverage of meteorological observations in the Muverans–Argentine massif and to better capture local variability driven by complex alpine topography.

This report documents the installation of the Solalex weather station and describes the local field site in its regional environmental and climatic context.

Location and description of field site

The Cergnement valley

The Cergnement valley is a high-alpine valley located in the Vaudois Alps, within the municipality of Bex, Switzerland. It lies

on the northern flank of the Grand Muveran and the Massif de l'Argentine and is accessible via a single road ending at the Solalex plateau.

The valley is characterized by steep surrounding rock faces, open alpine pastures, and a relatively flat valley floor in its upper part. Elevations in the catchment rise sharply from the valley floor to surrounding peaks exceeding 3,000 m a.s.l., resulting in a pronounced elevation gradient over short horizontal distances.

Climatically, Solalex experiences a typical alpine climate of the Alpes Vaudoises, with cold, snowy winters and cool summers observed in the region. Precipitation is high and largely controlled by orographic effects, while snow cover can persist for several months at valley floor level.

Location of the weather station

The AWS is located on the west side of the small settlement area of Solalex, on the bottom of the Cergnement valley (See *Table 1*). A public road provides easy access during the summer months.

Table 1 Station coordinates in CH1903+.

Latitude	2°57'6.96"
Longitude	1°12'6.394"
Altitude	1459 m a.s.l.

Figure 1. Map of the Solalex catchment with indication of the automated weather station.

Figure 2. Solalex automatic weather station.

Table 2. Instrumentation details.

Variable	Logging type	Unit	Measurem. interval (Scan)	Logging interval	Logging acronym	
LUFFT WS400-UMB Smart Weather Sensor						
Air temperature	Average	Degree Celsius (°C)	1 min	10 min	<i>AirTC_Avg</i>	
Relative humidity	Average	Per cent (%)	1 min	10 min	<i>RH</i>	
Atmospheric pressure	Average	Hectopascal (hPa)	1 min	10 min	<i>BP_hPa_Avg</i>	
Precipitation	Quantity	Totalize	Millimeters (mm)	1 min	10 min	<i>Rain_mm_Avg</i>
	Intensity	Average	Millimeters per hour (mm/h)	1 min	10 min	<i>Rain_I_Avg</i>
	Type	Average	Code	1	10 min	<i>Prec_type</i>
Dew point	Average	Degree Celsius (°C)	1 min	10 min	<i>DP_C_Avg</i>	
Young 05108-45-L Wind Monitor-HD, Alpine Version						
Wind speed	Average	Meters/second	1 min	10 min	<i>WS_ms_Avg</i>	
Wind direction	Sample	Degrees (°)	1 min	10 min	<i>WindDir_Avg</i>	

Technical details of sensors and measurement intervals

Instrumentation and Logging

The AWS is equipped with a Campbell Scientific CR300 data logger with a CELL215 cellular modem, a Young anemometer measuring wind direction and wind speed, and a LUFFT WS400-UMB compact all-in-one weather sensor measuring air temperature, relative humidity, air pressure, dew point temperature, precipitation intensity, precipitation type, and precipitation amount (derived).

The precipitation sensor operates using a 24 GHz Doppler radar, which measures the fall velocity of hydrometeors. Precipitation quantity and type are derived by correlating fall velocity and signal characteristics related to hydrometeor size.

Precipitation type is reported as a numerical classification value, for which the manufacturer recommends the following discrimination: 0 = no precipitation, 60 = liquid precipitation (e.g. rain), 70 = solid precipitation (e.g. snow), and 40 = unspecified or mixed precipitation. Intermediate values may

occur and represent transitional or uncertain precipitation conditions. The heated precipitation sensor allows reliable discrimination between liquid and solid precipitation, including during snowfall.

All sensors are scanned at a 1-minute interval, and data are logged as 10-minute average values. The logger clock is set to UTC time. See Table 2 for instrument details and logging parameters.

Electricity supply

The station's logger is connected to the 220V grid and supplies the AWS with 24V via a converter. Another converter in the station's box supplies 12V needed to power the logger.

Data transmission

The logger is equipped with an internal Campbell Scientific CELL215 4G LTE CAT1 modem, a Swisscom SIM-card and an antenna to allow for remote access and data backup using the University of Lausanne's FTP server.

Table 3 Header for AWS datasets

TIMESTAMP UTC+00	BattV	AirTC_ Avg	R H	DP_C_ Avg	BP_hPa_ Avg	Prec_ty pe	Rain_I_ Avg	Rain_mm_ Avg	Ws_ms_ Avg	Wind_Dir_ Avg
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Management and Maintenance

The AWS is regularly checked and maintained by the team of field technicians at the Institute of Earth Surface Dynamics, University of Lausanne. Each visit to the stations must be logged using a standardised online form, where changes,

Data curation and availability

Data will be checked for inconsistencies and erroneous data will be replaced by NaNs whenever the source of error is known.

Datasets are published annually, covering one full hydrological year (1 October – 30 September) on Zenodo, as part of the Vallon de Nant community. Datasets are published by year and will each have an assigned DOI.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/vdn/>

Datasets are available as tab delimited .txt files. Timestamps are in UTC following the format
yyyy-mm-dd hh:mm:ss

Suggested citation:

Miesen, F., Ballu, A. (year): Weather data from Solalex station, 01.10.20xx – 30.09.20xx. University of Lausanne. Zenodo. DOI: [url].

adaptations, damages etc. are reported. Request to access the log file must be addressed to terrain-idyst@unil.ch.

Any request for additional sensors at the station (including autonomous loggers, such as Hobo pendant loggers) must be directed to terrain-idyst@unil.ch

References

Guisan, A., Miesen, F., & Hiscox Baux, S. (2026). Solalex weather station data 2010 - 2018 [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18418479>

Miesen, F., Ballu, A., Kjellqvist, D., & Andersson, D. (2024). A new set of weather stations in Vallon de Nant, Alpes Vaudoises, Western Switzerland. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14527154>

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